

The Association between Physical Symptoms and Depression among Medical Students in Egypt

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ABSTRACT

Background: Medical students experience high psychological distress due to the demanding nature of their course, and this has significant implications for their physical and mental well-being. Few studies, however, have attempted to determine the association between depression and physical symptoms among Egyptian medical students.

Objective: This study aimed to assess the relationship between depression and physical symptoms among the Egyptian medical students.

Subjects and methods: A cross-sectional community-based study was conducted among medical students in Egypt before the start of the academic semester. Data were collected through an online questionnaire, including demographic information and two validated self-report scales: The Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) for depressive symptoms and the Patient Health Questionnaire-15 (PHQ-15) for physical symptom.

Results: 155 eligible students participated in the study, and they were predominantly females (76.1%) and fifth-year students (59.4%). The prevalence of moderate to severe depression was 66.5%, and 72.9% had moderate to severe physical symptoms. Depression was significantly positively correlated with physical symptoms ($r = .472$, $p < .01$). Social variables were examined as well: students in a relationship had fewer physical symptoms (Mean = 12.66, SD = 5.30) and depression scores (Mean = 10.55, SD = 4.74) than single students. Similarly, working students had lower depression scores (Mean = 10.77, SD = 4.73) and fewer physical symptoms (Mean = 12.26, SD = 5.15) than unemployed students.

Conclusion: The findings suggest a significant correlation between depression and physical symptoms among Egyptian medical students. Furthermore, having a relationship and working alongside studies appear to be associated with less depression and physical symptoms.

Keywords: Physical symptoms, Depression, Medical students, Egypt, Mental health, Quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Undergraduate students are a group of the community experience a transition from adolescence to adulthood, which is considered a very stressful phase in life, at same time medical education is stressful compared with non-medical education [1-2].

Due to requirement and challenges in academia, multiple tests, limited time, heavy work load as they must finish large amount of information and feeling inability to confront this load, psychological stress [3,4,5,6], blemish as inadequate academic progress or feeling highly stressed although perfect academic performance since high competition in medical schools [7]. Also, experiencing the absence of guidance from adults and missing financial and social support for the first time [8], all of these factors lead to compromised judgment, diminished attention, poor confidence, elevated anxiety, and depression [9].

It has been reported that medical colleges foster a toxic psychological environment [10], with a prevalence of depression 28.0% between medical students universally and highest prevalence in Africa and lowest in western countries. there is many factors correlated with depression in medical students as sex [11, 12], compulsive internet use [13, 14], age [14], academic year [12,14,15], satisfaction with career choice [11, 14], financial struggles [11, 14, 15, 16], education levels of parents [11], family-related problems [12], health status [12, 13], poor sleep quality [11, 16], disappointment with medical

education [15], dissatisfaction with social activities, and anxiety about future [3].

Depression can considerably affect student's achievement and fulfillments lowering them, also affect unfavorably relationships and communication [17, 18, 19, 20], as depression can be mistaken for stress brought on by more homework or tests, and the pressure of interacting socially with new patients and peers, it frequently goes undetected [18, 20]. Common symptoms of depression are depressed mood, diminished excitement or engagement in activities, appetite changes, sleeping problem, lack of energy, feelings of guilt or worthlessness, trouble in concentrating, and thoughts of death [21].

Also, depression characterized by physical symptoms such as accelerated rate of heartbeat, hyperventilation, sweating, shaking, exhaustion, and gastrointestinal disturbances including stomachaches or irritable bowel syndrome [22, 23], and it was reported that more severe physical symptoms indicate greater severity in depression and functional impairments [24, 25].

According to our knowledge, there is no sufficient studies studying correlation between physical symptoms and depression in medical students in Arabian countries, especially in Egypt. We tended to fill this gap assessing relationship between physical symptoms and depression in medical students in Egypt, analyzing factors associated to depression and

suggesting strategies to prevent and decrease depression prevalence and advance mental health for upcoming doctors.

METHODS

Study design: The study was a cross-sectional community – based study that examine the association between depression and physical symptoms among medical students in Egypt before starting the study semester and factors that could affect them.

Participants and recruitment: Students from various medical faculties enrolled to this study from various governorates of Egypt aged between 19 and 24 years were eligible to fill out the questionnaire. Through Google Form, the questionnaire was drawn up and students were invited to take part via advertisements, which were widely distributed on various social media networks [26]. The questionnaire was available for medical students for one week after semester starting from 8 February to 15 February 2025.

Data collection:

With the consent of the study participants, demographic data, two short validated self-administered questionnaires, and risk factors that were likely to affect the results of the questionnaire were collected. Demographic data included age and academic level. The risk factors that may affect the result of the questionnaire included relationship status, and whether the student intends to work while studying. The purpose of the self-administered PHQ-15 questionnaire was to identify a set of 15 somatic symptoms. With a three-point Likert scale, each of the 15 symptoms was given a score (Not bothered at all = 0, bothered a little = 1, bothered a lot = 2). The following was the interpretation of the PHQ-15 overall score: 0–4 minimal somatic symptoms, 5–9 low somatic symptoms, 10–14 medium somatic symptoms, and 15 or severe somatic symptoms [25, 27].

The depression module, the PHQ-9, used a four-point Likert scale (0 being not at all and 3 being almost every day) to score each of the nine DSM-IV criteria. It was not a screening tool; rather, it was used to track the presence of depression. According to the PHQ-9, symptoms can be classified as follows: 1-4 (Minimal or no depression), 5-9 (Mild depression), 10-14 (Moderate depression), 15-19 (Moderately severe depression) and 20-27 (Severe depression) [28].

Ethical Considerations: Under the registration number NCT06820814, this study was listed on ClinicalTrials.gov. Every participant gave their informed consent prior to filling out the survey. To ensure confidentiality and voluntary participation, the study was carried out in compliance with ethical guidelines Helsinki Declaration.

Statistical analysis

Data were collected and summarized according to the cross-sectional study. IBM (SPSS, version 22) software for windows was used to analyze all the collected data. Descriptive statistics were used to calculate the mean, standard deviation (SD), and percentages. Bivariate correlation was performed to assess the relationship between depression and physical symptoms. A P-value ≤ 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

RESULTS

The survey was answered by 158 persons, only 155 met the study's eligibility criteria including 118 (76.1%) women and 37 (23.9%) men, all participants were Egyptian medical students. The participant's demographic characteristics were presented in table (1). The majority of participants were fifth-year students (59.4%), with smaller proportions from other academic years. Most participants were single (82.6%), while 11.6% were in a relationship. Only 16.7% reported working alongside their studies.

Table (1): The participant's demographic characteristics

Study level	No. (%)
1 st Year	17 (11%)
2 nd Year	7 (4.5%)
3 rd Year	11 (7.1%)
4 th year	28 (18.1%)
5 th year	92 (59.4%)
Gender	No. (%)
male	37 (23.9%)
female	118 (76.1%)
Relationship Status	No. (%)
Single	128 (82.6%)
in a relationship	18 (11.6%)
Prefer not to say	9 (5.8%)
Work Alongside Studying	No. (%)
yes	26 (16.7%)
no	125 (80.6%)
Prefer not to say	4(2.6%)

□ No.: The number of cases or participants (actual count), □ (%): The percentage of this number relative to the total sample.

The physical symptoms among participants, assessed using the PHQ-15, are mentioned in table (2). The most commonly reported symptoms were low energy or fatigue, trouble sleeping, and back pain, with 59.4%, 41.3%, and 44.5% of participants, respectively, reporting being significantly bothered by these symptoms. The average PHQ-15 score was 12.98 ± 5.27, indicating a high prevalence of physical symptoms among the sample.

Table (2): The physical symptoms among participants, assessed using the PHQ-15

Physical Symptoms	Not bothered at all n (%)	Bothered a little n (%)	Bothered a lot n (%)
Stomach pain	53 (34.2 %)	73 (47.1 %)	29 (18.7%)
Back pain	25 (16.1%)	61 (39.4%)	69 (44.5%)
Pain in your arms, legs, or joints (knees, hips, etc.)	37 (23.9%)	68 (43.9%)	50 (32.3%)
Menstrual cramps or other problems with your periods WOMEN ONLY	59 (38.1%)	47 (30.3%)	49 (31.3%)
Headaches	26 (16.8%)	81 (52.3%)	48 (31%)
Chest pain	84 (54.2%)	60 (38.7%)	11 (7.1%)
Dizziness	69 (44.5%)	69 (44.5%)	17 (11%)
Fainting spells	128 (82.6%)	24 (15.5%)	3 (1.9%)
Feeling your heart pound or race	55 (35.5%)	66 (42.6%)	34 (21.9%)
Shortness of breath	62 (40%)	61 (39.4%)	32 (20.6%)
Pain or problems during sexual intercourse	152 (98%)	3 (2%)	0 (0%)
Constipation, loose bowels, or diarrhea	57 (36.8%)	57 (36.8%)	41 (26.5%)
Nausea, gas, or indigestion	50 (32.3%)	62 (40%)	43 (27.7%)
Feeling tired or having low energy	8 (5.2%)	55 (35.5%)	92 (59.4%)
Trouble sleeping	30 (19.4%)	61 (39.4%)	64 (41.3%)

□ n.: The number of cases or participants (actual count)., □ (%): The percentage of this number relative to the total sample.

Depressive symptoms, as assessed by the PHQ-9, are presented in table (3). The mean PHQ-9 score was **11.83 ± 5.04**, reflecting moderate depression. Surprisingly, **66.5%** of participants reported **moderate to severe depressive** symptoms. The most commonly reported symptoms of depression were feeling tired or having little energy (**23.9%**) and trouble sleeping (**29%**), and **3.9%** of participants reporting suicidal ideation or being better off dead nearly every day.

Table (3): Depressive symptoms, assessed using the PHQ-9

Depressive Symptoms	Not at all	Several Days	More than half the days	Nearly every day
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Little interest or pleasure in doing things	16 (10.3 %)	70 (45.2 %)	47 (30.3 %)	22 (14.2 %)
Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless	17 (11%)	73 (74.1%)	36 (23.2%)	29 (18.7%)
Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	24 (15.5%)	44 (28.4%)	42 (27.1%)	45 (29%)
Feeling tired or having little energy	8 (5.2%)	62 (40%)	31) 48%(37 (23.9%)
Poor appetite or overeating	35 (22.6%)	55 (35.5%)	32 (20.6%)	33 (21.3%)
Feeling bad about yourself or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down	39 (25.2%)	53 (34.2%)	31 (20%)	32 (20.6%)
Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	43 (27.7%)	55 (35.5%)	34 (21.9%)	14.8) 23%(
Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed. Or the opposite being so figety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	66 (42.6%)	58 (37.4%)	21 (13.5%)	10 (6.5%)
Thoughts that you would be better off dead, or of hurting yourself	99 (63.9%)	29 (18.7%)	21 (13.5%)	6 (3.9%)

□ n.: The number of cases or participants (actual count), □ (%): The percentage of this number relative to the total sample.

Table (4) showed the correlation between depression and physical symptoms among the participants. A Pearson correlation was conducted to assess the strength and direction of the relationship. The results revealed a significant positive correlation between depression and physical symptoms ($r = .472, p < .01$), suggesting that higher levels of depressive symptoms were associated with more physical symptoms.

Table (4): Pearson correlation coefficient between depression and physical symptoms among the participants.

Variables	Depression	Physical Symptoms
Depression	1	0.472**
Physical Symptoms	0.472**	1

Note: $p < 0.01$ (2-tailed).

The various physical symptoms levels and depression levels among the participants were shown in table (5) and table (6) respectively together with the mean scores and standard deviations for each group. The findings demonstrated that the mean progressively increased across the levels with the severity of physical symptoms and depression.

Table (5): Physical symptoms levels among the participants

Level of Physical Symptoms	Mean (SD)
Minimal Physical Symptoms	3.36 (0.67)
Low Physical Symptoms	7.32 (1.27)
Medium Physical Symptoms	12.1 (1.41)
High Physical Symptoms	18.0 (2.65)

SD: Standard deviation.

Table (6): Depression levels among the participants

Level of Depression	Mean (SD)
Minimal Depression	3.44 (0.72)
Low Depression	7.02 (1.29)
Medium Depression	11.84 (1.42)
Moderately severe depression	16.68 (1.47)
High Depression	22 (2.52)

SD: Standard deviation.

Stratified analysis based on relationship status showed that students in relationships reported lower physical symptoms (Mean = 12.66, SD = 5.30) and depression scores (Mean = 10.55, SD = 4.74) compared to single students (Table 7 & table 8). Similarly, participants working alongside their studies exhibited lower physical symptoms (Mean = 12.26, SD = 5.15) and depression scores (Mean = 10.77, SD = 4.73) compared to those not working (Mean = 13.12, SD =

5.30 and mean = 12.04, SD = 5.09 respectively) (Table 9 & table 10).

Table (7): Prevalence of physical symptoms (PHQ-15) among medical students stratified by marital status

Students In Relationships VS single students (Physical Symptoms)	
(n)	Mean (SD)
In Relationships (18)	12.66 (5.30)
single students (128)	12.91 (5.34)

SD: Standard deviation, n.: The number of cases or participants (actual count).

Table (8): Prevalence of depression (PHQ-9) among medical students stratified by marital status

Students In Relationships VS single students (Depression)	
(n)	Mean (SD)
In Relationships (18)	10.55 (4.74)
single students (128)	11.99 (5.18)

SD: Standard Deviation, n.: The number of cases or participants (actual count).

Table (9): Prevalence of physical symptoms among students who are working alongside their studies compared to those who are not working

Students Working VS Not Working students (Physical Symptoms)	
(n)	Mean (SD)
Working Students (26)	12.26 (5.15)
Not Working Students (125)	13.12 (5.30)

SD: Standard deviation, n.: The number of cases or participants (actual count).

Table (10): Prevalence of depression among students who are working alongside their studies compared to those who are not working

Students Working VS Not Working students (Depression)	
(n)	Mean (SD)
Working Students (26)	10.769 (4.73)
Not Working Students (125)	12.04 (5.09)

SD: Standard deviation, n.: The number of cases or participants (actual count).

The scatter plot visualization further demonstrated the positive correlation between depression and physical symptoms, supporting the statistical findings. The results indicate that higher depressive symptoms are significantly associated with greater physical complaints among Egyptian medical students (Fig. 1).

Higher depression scores were typically linked to more physical symptoms, according to the scatter plot's positive connection. The statistical study revealed a substantial positive connection ($r = .472, p < .01$), which is supported by this graphic portrayal.

Figure (1): scatter plot.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to investigate the correlation between physical and depressed symptoms in medical students in Egypt, particularly at the commencement of the academic semester. This research was inspired by a study by **Abdelaziz et al.** [29] in Bahrain, which found a strong link between physical and depressive symptoms in medical students. Additionally, earlier studies on the prevalence of depression among medical students in Egypt have looked into various factors affecting their mental health. Our study expands on these findings by investigating other social factors, like relationship status and employment, to see how they might influence depressive symptoms.

Our investigation revealed a significant correlation between physical and depressive symptoms ($r = .472$, $p < .01$). This observation underscored the relationship between the mental health issues experienced by medical students and their physical ailments, corroborating findings from prior research. According to our results, 72.9% of participants exhibited moderate to severe physical symptoms, while 66.5% reported medium to high levels of depressive symptoms. These elevated percentages highlight the substantial psychological and physical adversities encountered by medical students, potentially resulting in decreased academic performance, increased risk of burnout, and a compromised quality of life. An important dimension of our research is the impact of social determinants on depressive symptoms.

Students in relationships reported lower depression scores (Mean = 10.55, SD = 4.74) compared to those who were single (Mean = 11.99, SD = 5.18). In a comparable manner, individuals engaged in employment demonstrated diminished levels of depressive symptoms (Mean = 10.77, SD = 4.73) when juxtaposed with their non-employed peers (Mean = 12.04, SD = 5.09). This finding challenges the widely held belief that increased responsibilities, such as those

associated with employment, heighten stress levels and aggravate mental health conditions. Conversely, our findings indicated that working students may derive benefits from elements such as social support within the workplace, enhanced financial autonomy, and effective time management, which may serve as protective mechanisms against depressive disorders. It was shown that social support in work may have a positive impact on productivity and psychological well-being [30].

Even though work seems to provide some protective advantages, it raises an important question: why do students who balance work and school report lower depression levels even when they have less time for their studies? One reasonable argument is that work offers a defined daily routine, fosters social interactions, and gives a sense of purpose all of which may help reduce the stressors related to scholastic obligations. Additionally, the financial stability and support that come with working in a professional setting may help to lessen some of the stressors that lead to the depressed symptoms that are seen in students who are not employed.

Nonetheless, the fact that a considerable number of students report medium to high depressive symptoms levels is worrisome. The outcomes of severe depression typically entail suicidal thoughts, feelings of worthlessness, poor sleep, excessive sleeping and fatigue, or appetite changes [31]. Each of these symptoms has tremendous effects on students' academic achievement, interpersonal relationships, and future employment.

Due to the high rates of medium to high depression within this population, it is critical for university authorities and policymakers to actively intervene by initiating sustained mental health programs, making counseling available, and lastly, creating a more receptive academic culture that encourages active participation so as to enhance students' general well-being.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Despite the fact that our research details some aspects of the connection between medical student's depression and their physical symptoms, some key limitations do exist. First, the cross-sectional nature of this study restricts the inference of casual relationships. Longitudinal studies are required to analyze the progression of depressive symptoms and physical complaints over a period of time. Second, the study was based on self-reported data, which is a subject to recall biases and social desirability bias. Moreover, this sample, in comparison with other Egyptian medical students, is more relevant, but further research which compares several faculties or universities might shed lighter on the problem. Further studies should also target the reduction of depression and physical concerns exhibited by medical students. Looking into exercise, mindfulness, and institutional support programs can build focus strategies to enhance student's wellbeing.

Moreover, the relative workplace supports and the social support systems warrant further exploration as potential mental health buffers.

CONCLUSION

Results suggest that there was a significant correlation between depression and physical symptoms within Egyptian medical students at the beginning of the academic semester. The data also indicated that social factors like relationship status and working alongside with studying can help decrease levels of depression and physical symptoms.

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